

The presence of green, immature, and husked grains (brown rice) was significantly higher in mechanically harvested rice than in hand-harvested and threshed rice for both varieties (see

table). The higher moisture percentage in the combine-harvested rice is due to the larger amount of green and immature grains, which may be attributed to the superior threshing efficiency of the

combine harvester. Total milling and head rice recovery in combine-harvested rice were 1.3-1.7 and 3.9-5.0% lower, respectively, than those in hand-harvested rice. □

Grain quality of some promising medium-grain rices

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We compared the physicochemical characteristics of some promising

medium-grain rice breeding lines with standard varieties IR6 and KS282. Rices were grown under similar environmental conditions in yield trials during 1988-90.

Eight of the 14 lines approached the standard varieties in kernel length and length-breadth ratio. Head rice recovery was 49.2-57.4% (see table). Only PK1385-9-1-B-1-1 gave slightly higher head rice than KS282. Broken rice

among lines tested was 14.0-20.0%. Proportionate elongation on cooking of eight lines was at par with that of IR6 and KS282. None of the lines approached KS282 in protein content. All lines, as well as the standard varieties, had high amylose content and low gelatinization temperature (alkali spreading value of 6-7). Gel consistency values ranged from 32 to 64 mm. □

Physicochemical characteristics of some promising medium-grain lines.

Variety or line	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	Length-breadth ratio	Milling recovery		Proportionate elongation on cooking	Protein content (%)	Amylose content (%)	Alkali spreading value	Gel consistency (mm)
				Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)					
PK1385-9-1-B-1-1	6.51	1.97	3.30	57.4	14.6	1.58	8.38	28.2	6.5	64
PK1385-9-1-B-1-12	6.51	1.95	3.34	55.7	14.0	1.63	9.00	28.2	6.4	47
PK1385-9-1-B-1-13	6.23	1.96	3.18	55.0	15.9	1.70	9.18	28.5	6.5	60
PK2480-7-3-1	6.62	1.76	3.76	55.3	16.0	1.70	8.38	29.5	6.5	47
PK3303-7-2	6.85	1.82	3.76	54.6	15.5	1.60	8.64	28.0	6.6	53
PK3305-15-1	6.84	1.81	3.78	53.5	17.2	1.61	8.73	28.5	6.5	56
PK3327-13-1	6.28	1.97	3.19	55.1	15.0	1.72	8.02	27.5	6.5	55
PK3358-13-3-2	6.47	1.84	3.52	54.0	16.6	1.75	8.38	29.5	6.5	47
PK3717-9	6.79	1.84	3.69	54.7	16.1	1.73	8.02	28.7	6.2	45
PK3717-12	6.75	1.85	3.65	53.0	17.3	1.75	8.46	28.0	6.5	42
PK3727-2	6.72	1.85	3.63	53.8	17.0	1.71	8.02	28.0	6.4	50
PK3721-5	6.74	1.87	3.60	56.0	15.2	1.65	8.28	28.5	6.5	47
PK3817-33	6.80	1.86	3.65	55.5	15.7	1.71	8.02	27.2	6.3	40
PK3849-18	6.81	1.82	3.74	49.2	20.0	1.64	8.12	28.0	6.5	32
IR6	6.72	1.84	3.65	55.7	15.2	1.70	7.62	29.1	6.6	41
KS282	6.84	1.79	3.82	57.0	14.6	1.74	9.87	28.3	6.5	46

Stress tolerance

Elite F₁ rice hybrids for low-light monsoon areas

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Low light is one of the major constraints to rice production during the wet season (WS). We compared tolerance for low light in selected F₁ rice hybrid combinations (Table 1) with the best low-light-tolerant standard check Swarnaprabha, during the 1990 WS and 1991 WS. The crop was grown in 1.2-m²

field plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing and fertilized with 60 kg N/ha.

Wooden screens were used to create low light (50% sunlight) conditions from 40 d after planting to harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 340 call cm² per d). The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. The two light treatments were in the main plots and the hybrids in the subplots. Leaf area index (LAI) at flowering, total dry matter (TDM), yield, and harvest index (HI) were recorded at harvest. The photosynthetic rate (P_n) of the boot

leaf at flowering was measured with the LI-6000 Portable Photosynthesis System at near saturated light (above 1,000 µE/m² per s).

P_n, crop photosynthesis (P_n × LAI), TDM, HI, and yield were consistently higher for the hybrids from the pollen parent Vajram, i.e., IR54752 A/Vajram during 1990 and from IR62829 A/Vajram during 1991. The yield, TDM, and HI were also the highest in these hybrids under low light. They were at par or even superior in yield to Swarnaprabha, especially under low light.

Hybrid IR62829 A/Vajram recorded the highest yield during the 1991 WS at